

It appears from the above equations that the lattice water is lost between 80-120°, while the coordinated water is lost at slightly higher temperature around 280°. The coordinated amine usually decomposes in the range 140-200°, the individual temperature, however, varies with the nature of amine and complex. The azo groups are lost completely around 380° and thereafter, the formation of the metal oxide occurs and no decomposition takes place upto 1000°.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Zinc(II) with Dibasic Acids and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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As a part of the programme on d¹⁰ metal complexes, some penta-coordinated zinc(II) complexes with nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands were reported¹⁻³ earlier from this laboratory. More recently Sharma and Jain reported⁴ some mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with dibasic acids and primary and heterocyclic amines as secondary ligands. This communication reports some penta-coordinated mixed ligand complexes of zinc(II) succinate, malonate, glutarate or adipate with

thiocyanate and nitrogen donor ligands like α -picoline and morpholine.

Experimental

Ethanolic solutions of zinc chloride, the organic acid and potassium thiocyanate were mixed in stoichiometric ratio and filtered directly into an ethanolic solution of α -picoline or morpholine. The resulting precipitate was suction filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride/methanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Zinc, thiocyanate and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Carbon and hydrogen were microanalysed. The conductance measurements were carried out on 10⁻³ M solutions in pyridine using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102, with a dip type cell. Infrared spectra were recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ by Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Thermogravimetric studies⁵ were carried out in a manually operated thermobalance. Analytical and physical data for the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

As the α -picoline complexes take up moisture and decompose due to hydrolysis, these were kept in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance values (Table 1) of all the compounds indicate them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes. In the ir spectra, the stretching bands due to C=O of malonic, succinic, glutaric and adipic acids at 1724, 1730, 1695 and 1700 cm⁻¹, respectively have been lowered to 1630, 1635, 1630 and 1610 cm⁻¹ in the corresponding complexes indicating the coordination of acids through carboxylate oxygen⁶. The bands appearing at 2050-2080 and 785-860 cm⁻¹ due to ν (C-N) and ν (C-S), respectively indicate the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate group⁶. The bands at ~3210 and ~1115 cm⁻¹, due to

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF MIXED LIGAND ZINC(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	m.p. °C	%Zn	%thio- cyanate	%N	%C	%H	Δ_M mhos [#]
K[Zn(α -pic)M.H ₂ O(NCS)]	210(d)	17.23 (17.41)*	15.2 (15.45)	7.55 (7.41)	31.81 (31.78)	3.01 (2.98)	66
K[Zn(α -pic)S.H ₂ O(NCS)]	200(d)	16.52 (16.79)	14.76 (14.89)	7.00 (7.17)	33.67 (33.88)	3.42 (3.36)	68
K[Zn(α -pic)G.H ₂ O(NCS)]	230(d)	16.02 (16.20)	14.27 (14.37)	6.78 (6.90)	35.34 (35.51)	3.90 (3.72)	74
K[Zn(α -pic)A.H ₂ O(NCS)]	250(d)	15.41 (15.65)	13.76 (13.90)	6.42 (6.67)	37.00 (37.18)	3.8 (4.0)	70
K[Zn(moph)M.H ₂ O(NCS)]	112	17.42 (17.69)	15.58 (15.73)	7.67 (7.57)	26.74 (26.98)	3.62 (3.54)	71
K[Zn(moph)S.H ₂ O(NCS)]	105	16.88 (17.05)	15.01 (15.12)	7.22 (7.30)	27.98 (28.16)	4.08 (3.94)	69
K[Zn(moph)G.H ₂ O(NCS)]	138	16.27 (16.45)	14.51 (14.60)	6.86 (7.04)	30.00 (30.19)	4.50 (4.31)	78
K[Zn(moph)A.H ₂ O(NCS)]	172	15.66 (15.89)	14.00 (14.10)	6.57 (6.80)	31.84 (32.08)	4.74 (4.65)	75

*Figures in parentheses indicate calculated values. M=malonate, S=succinate, G=glutarate and A=adipate; α -pic= α -picoline, moph=morpholine; d=decomposed.

Based on theoretical values of molecular weights.

ν (N-H) stretch and ν (C-O-C) stretch show -ve and +ve shift respectively with respect to free morpholine and indicate morpholine coordinates through nitrogen atom⁶. Similarly, the sharp bands at ~ 2940 and ~ 1040 cm^{-1} are attributed to the presence of N-coordinated α -pic⁷. The broad band at ~ 3400 cm^{-1} and sharp band at ~ 870 cm^{-1} in both the complexes indicates the presence of coordinated water molecule⁸.

Thermal decomposition: Thermal decomposition of morpholine complexes reveals no weight loss at 100° indicating that the water molecules are not in the lattice. The different products from the weight loss obtained by thermal decomposition are as follows:

where L = anion of dibasic acids.

In the light of the above evidences, it is suggested that all the complexes are five coordinated anionic complexes.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Cadmium(II) with Oxine as Primary Ligand and Heterocyclic and Aromatic Amines as Secondary Ligands

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Oxine is known to possess both antifungal and antibacterial properties¹⁻³. It also behaves as an uninegative bidentate chelating ligand having ON potential donor sites. The present note describes the synthesis and characterisation of some

mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) and cadmium(II) with nitrogen donor heterocyclic and aromatic bases.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of metal oxinates: To an aqueous solution of metal chloride (2.36 g in case of cobaltous chloride and 2.01 g in case of cadmium chloride), sodium acetate (5 g) was added and warmed to $65-70^\circ$. The ethanolic solution of oxine (3.0 g) was added to it separately when light brown amorphous cobalt oxinate or light yellow amorphous cadmium oxinate separated out immediately. The metal oxinates thus formed were allowed to stand overnight and then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes: To an ethanolic suspension of metal oxinate nitrogen donor ligands were added separately and refluxed for 1-2 hr. The compounds were then filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The metal contents of the complexes were estimated by EDTA titration method and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Conductance of the complexes was measured in 10^{-3} M acetone solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes were recorded in 10^{-3} M DMF-base solution using Hilgerwatt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Analytical data of the complexes prepared are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation are of the type $[\text{ML}_2\text{L}'_2]$ and $[\text{ML}_2\text{L}']$ where M = cobalt(II), cadmium(II); LH = oxine; L' = pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline, quinoline, piperidine, 2,6-lutidine, 4-aminopyridine, quinaldine, morpholine; L'' = *o*-phenylenediamine, 1,10-phenanthroline or 2-2'-bipyridine. The complexes show low conductance values in acetone medium (Δ_M ranges from 8.5 to 15 mhos cm^2) indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectra of the ligand, metal oxinate and mixed ligand complexes are informative. The ir active bands at 1500, 1280 and 900 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the phenolic OH deformation modes coupled with C-O stretching modes ($\nu_{\text{CO}} + \nu_{\text{OH}}$) and to the out of plane deformation vibration (σ OH), respectively. The absence of these bands in the spectra of the metal oxinates indicates that the proton of the hydroxyl group is replaced by the metal ions. The bands at 1450, 1260, 1095 and 1060 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both heterocyclic ligands and mixed ligand complexes are characteristic of substituted pyridine ring vibration⁴. A medium broad band appears at ~ 3450 cm^{-1} region in case of metal oxinates assignable⁵ to ν (O-H) of